

54th Days of Preventive Medicine International Congress

27-30. September 2022.
Niš, Serbia

BOOK OF ABSTRACT

Public Health Institute Niš

Faculty of Medicine,
University of Niš

Serbian Medical Society

Niš, 2022.

*122 years of Public Health Protection in Serbia
from regular preventive activities
to great challenges in COVID-19 pandemic time*

*122 године заштите јавног здравља у Србији
од редовних превентивних активности
до великих изазова у време пандемије COVID-19*

**PUBLIC HEALTH INSTITUTE NIŠ
FACULTY OF MEDICINE, UNIVERSITY OF NIŠ
SERBIAN MEDICAL SOCIETY, NIŠ**

**54TH DAYS OF PREVENTIVE MEDICINE
INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS**

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MAIN TOPICS

- **Environment and health**
- **Nutrition and health**
- **Microbiology today**
- **Current parasitosis**
- **Theoretical and practical problems of communicable diseases**
- **Theoretical and practical problems of non-communicable diseases**
- **Health promotion – challenges and solutions**
- **Preventive aspect of healthcare organization**
- **Application of information and communication tools in the health care system**

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10. MELATONIN-CONTAINING DIETARY SUPPLEMENTS AVAILABLE AT THE SERBIAN MARKET

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Objectives: The aim of this research was to identify and assess the characteristics of dietary supplements (DS) of melatonin available at the Serbian market. **Methods:** DS available on the market were identified using the Dietary products' database (Ministry of Health) and online pharmacies' inventories. Data on specific DS were obtained from their labels. **Results:** A total of 24 DS containing melatonin have been identified. Declared recommended daily doses ranged from 0.5 mg to 3 mg (average – 1 mg). Doses up to 1 mg were recommended for jet lag, whereas larger doses were recommended for insomnia. The majority of DS were in solid forms (tablets and capsules, 71%) and the remainder in aerosol form. Around half of the DS (54%) contained other substances such as botanicals (valerian, lemon balm), magnesium, folic acid, myo-inositol. Most of the health claims on melatonin DS were compliant with the national regulations (80%). Excipients with the potential for causing adverse effects were present in 37% of melatonin-containing DS. **Conclusion:** As the demand for melatonin-containing DS is expected to rise, healthcare professionals should be aware of the differences between the available DS in order to counsel DS users to the best of their knowledge

Keywords: dietary supplements; nutritional supplements; melatonin; insomnia